

PARAMETRIC MODEL BASED ON GEOMETRIC SHAPES FOR OPTIMIZING THE DESIGN PROCESS IN GRAPHIC DESIGN.

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***Abstract.** This thesis examines the role of a parametric model based on geometric shapes in optimizing the design process in graphic design. The aim of the study is to develop a parametric approach that systematizes the design process and enhances its efficiency. In the course of the research, the constructive, compositional, and functional capabilities of geometric shapes were analyzed, and a step-by-step parametric model was proposed based on these characteristics. The results demonstrate that the proposed model reduces redundant operations in the design process, saves time, and improves visual accuracy.*

***Keywords:** CorelDRAW, graphic design, geometric shapes, parametric model, design process, composition, optimization.*

INTRODUCTION

In modern graphic design practice, optimizing the design process is one of the important scientific and practical challenges. In a digital graphics environment, the creation of design objects is a multi-stage process that requires a systematic approach to improve efficiency. Standard geometric shapes play a crucial role as fundamental constructive elements in forming visual compositions in graphic design.

Therefore, developing a parametric model based on geometric shapes for optimizing the design process in graphic design is considered a relevant research problem. Therefore, developing a parametric model based on geometric shapes for optimizing the design process in graphic design is considered one of the noteworthy research issues.

Modern vector graphics software, particularly CorelDRAW, widely utilizes standard geometric shapes in object creation. Tools such as Rectangle, Ellipse,

Polygon, Star, and Common Shapes allow for rapid generation of graphical elements and flexible parameter adjustment. These shapes enable precise control over dimensions, proportions, and configurations, allowing designers to create complex compositions efficiently and accurately.

MAIN PART

As a result of the research, a parametric model aimed at optimizing the design process is proposed. This model is based on the systematic use of geometric shapes through parametric control and organizes the design process into sequential stages:

1. Creation of basic shapes stage. The initial constructive model of the composition is formed using standard geometric shapes.

2. Parametric configuration stage. Visual elements are adjusted through parameters to ensure precision and flexibility.

3. Transformation and modification stage. Shapes are transformed to create complex visual structures.

4. Compositional synthesis stage. Elements are integrated into a final visual system based on compositional principles.

5. Process optimization stage. Efficiency and time-saving are achieved through parametric control.

The model interprets graphic design as a parametric system and transforms it into a controllable process.

Within the proposed model, the functional and parametric capabilities of geometric shapes are systematized (Table 1).

Table 1. Functional and Parametric Characteristics of Geometric Shapes.

Instrument	Function	Parametric Capabilities	Role in Design
Rectangle	Creates rectangular and square shapes.	Adjusting dimensions (width and height); rotation (angle control); corner parameter adjustment; contour (line) thickness and style control.	Geometric shapes in graphic design not only form the compositional structure and ensure visual expression, but also increase the efficiency of the design process, enabling precise and rapid execution of drawings.
Ellipse	Creates circular and elliptical shapes.	Adjusting dimensions (width and height); creating segment shapes (arc/pie) via start and end angles; rotation; contour property control.	
Polygon	Creates multi-sided geometric shapes.	Adjusting the number of sides; modifying dimensions; rotation; contour control.	
Star	Creates star-shaped (multi-pointed) figures.	Adjusting dimensions; controlling number of points; modifying inner and outer radius; rotation; contour control.	
Common Shapes	Creates predefined geometric and pictographic shapes.	Modifying parameters (proportion, deformation, rotation); contour control.	

CONCLUSION

The results of the study demonstrate the effectiveness of a parametric model based on geometric shapes in optimizing the design process in graphic design. The proposed model enables a structured, step-by-step organization of the design process, the implementation of parametric control, and improved visual accuracy.

Furthermore, this approach can be effectively applied both in design practice and in educational contexts as a methodological tool. A parametric model based on geometric shapes can be considered one of the promising directions for optimizing design activities.

In this regard, standard geometric shapes in CorelDRAW serve as an important practical tool for optimizing the graphic design process.

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